

Protest Songs In Philippines: The Voice Of People

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
November 06, 2021

Accepted:
June 07, 2022

Keywords :

Protest Songs,
Philippines

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.6619156

Abstract

Music is essential in protesting, as it allows ordinary people, as well as amateur and professional musicians, to raise their voices in a loud call for justice. Singing allows ordinary people, as well as amateur and professional musicians, to raise their voices in a loud call for justice. It is a personal and sensual act that has more force and persuasiveness than simple speech, whether done alone or as part of a group. Singing is a personal and sensuous act that has greater power and persuasiveness than plain speaking. Given that music is ubiquitous, that it exists in all cultures, and that it is fundamentally owned by all humans, it serves as a medium and a performance act that is fundamentally recognizable, familiar, and translatable. As a result, it has the potential to bridge social and political divides, or at the very least to reveal our shared humanity. In the first place, making music – or musicking – allows individuals to express themselves and celebrate not just who they are, but also who they aspire to become. Music, on the other hand, is not necessarily pleasant or utopian. Music, like any other medium, has the ability to be used for the sake of malignant propagandistic propaganda. It has the power to misinform, proselytize, provoke, and exclude; singers, song lyrics, and performance activities may, in reality, be a part of the systems that perpetuate oppressive structures and practices, as well as the systems that perpetuate oppressive structures and practices. The emotive, persuasive, ethical, and optimistic power of song is demonstrated through the use of music to oppose injustice, confront inequity, rise above hatred and fear, and speak out against the normalization of prejudice, racism, sexism, homophobia, and a slew of other anti-democratic, antihuman behaviors.

Introduction

According to President Rodrigo Duterte's government, political music is making a return in the Philippines, and it is gaining popularity as the country's protest movement grows in strength. Protest music is neither a trend nor a genre defined by certain musical genres or structures, nor is it a subgenre of protest music. It is a combination of both. It draws attention to a visible and contemporary socioeconomic issue that has been affecting some segments of the general population for some time. Despite the fact that it is not a music scene in the traditional sense, it is a movement with a common message and objective. It was under Ferdinand Marcos' dictatorship that some of the most effective modern protest music in the Philippines was written between 1960 and 1980, particularly under the influence of the regime's repressive policies. Throughout this era, revolutionary organizations issued volumes of songbooks as part of their attempts to strengthen the people's battle for true freedom and democracy. As part of the process of political organization, these works were dispersed around the country and carried out in several sites at the same time. The goal of the artists was not to provide a fitting soundtrack for the revolution, but rather to express themselves artistically via their work. To put it another way, the music was designed to arouse worries about society structures and the ways of altering them at their most fundamental level.

Protest songs in Politics

Protest songs were the most effective means of expressing the voice and demands of the people at that pivotal historical time in history. While Bayan Ko was a popular protest song during the Martial Law and EDSA Revolution periods in the 1970s and 1980s, it is more accurately described as a time capsule of the Philippine nationalist struggle for genuine independence and socio-political transformation, which can be traced back to the colonial era. During the Inang Bayan independence wars in 1898, during which the Ku Klux Klan and the Philippine Revolution battled for independence, the song Bayan Ko was produced in response. This deeply rooted nationalist battle would continue throughout the Philippine War for Independence from the Americans and, subsequently, against the Japanese. As Martial Law lasted, this nationalist sentiment would resurface, culminating in the EDSA People Power I Revolution in 1986. EDSA in 1986, protest songs like Handog ng Pilipino sa Mundo and Magkaisa, on the other side, communicated to a global audience the concluding spirit that the people had already achieved, as well as ideals and concepts like as hope, freedom, justice and

democracy that the people had already won. Untangling the EDSA People Power I Revolution from its veiled message resulted in nothing more than a revolution that was never fully completed. A social psychologist, Dr. Patricia L. Licuanan, cautioned in 1987 that the core and spirit of the People Power movement were in risk of being lost and that the movement was on the verge of being fashionable. According to Dr. Licuanan, restoring the Philippines to its prehistoric state is more than just about restoring the nation to its prehistoric state; it is also about being really fair by dividing the rewards of success that have accumulated as a consequence of the country's economic progress equally. Specifically, she believes that the following activities can help achieve this goal: (1) raising critical consciousness, which entails critically analyzing and discussing Philippine reality/history and context; (2) mobilizing people to participate in political activities; and (3) developing ideas or visions of a society and government that the people want to live under.

A History of Protest Songs

It was in the early 1970s that the popularity of music performed by Filipino singers and ensembles began to grow. Throughout history, the musical genre known as Manila Sound has developed and prospered. The popular music of the United Kingdom and the United States served as inspiration for the development of the genre. In addition to the employment of caustic and chastising tones, the usage of Taglish, and the depiction of apparently incongruous and upsetting daily situations², there are many other features that may appeal to the younger generation. While summary executions, unlawful detentions, food blockades, and other violent measures continued to be imposed on the populace by the dictatorship's mailed hand, this decree created the appearance of a climate of freedom for artists. This was true even though it was issued by the same government that had declared Martial Law in 1989. By looking at the many roles that music played during the period of Martial Law and the history of the system, we can see that music served a range of functions in Filipino culture. Contrary to popular perception, during which open political activity was no longer authorized, Martial Law was also an era of innovation in terms of expressing dissatisfaction and examining social problems. It has been shown that informal musical experiences at home are associated with various aspects of language development in younger children, such as pre-schoolers. The findings of a study conducted in the United Kingdom by Politico et al. revealed that rhythm perception and production were the strongest predictors of early childhood phonological awareness, while melody perception was the strongest predictor of grammar acquisition, revealing a previously unknown link in developmental research. Barrett and colleagues performed another pre-school study in which they investigated the attitudes and perspectives held by early childhood and care practitioners in Australia about the role of music in young children's learning. Barrett et al. A favorable attitude toward music was indicated by practitioners, despite the fact that they had no official credentials and had no prior personal music learning experience. Their opinions, on the other hand, were skewed toward music as a leisure and enjoyable activity, with little support for the concept that music might be utilized to promote larger areas of children's growth and learning.

The power of Music in Politics

Music and words have the ability to bring people together on a deeper level. Because it triggers a memory in some manner in practically everyone, music provides a significant experience for everyone who listens to it. Incorporating music into the classroom as a learning tool may assist to bring even the drabest academic topic to life by adding some vigor and excitement into the conversation. If you're talking about politics, the common ideas and concepts that can be taken from song lyrics help students connect more quickly, comprehend the message more easily, and expound on the message that is being tried to be communicated by the topic message. More in-depth analysis of the underlying information necessary for theoretical argument is made possible, which is advantageous not just in political theory but also in other social science domains such as sociology. As a result, it shouldn't come as a surprise that music is often employed in campaign advertisements. When people are able to connect the words of a song to a larger vision that they wish to put into action but that is periodically repressed in some manner, they have gained freedom of speech. According to the author's discussion in the article, it is in this environment that music may be used as a tool not just for learning and self-expression, but also as a catalyst for societal transformation. It is possible that upheavals in political and social ideas are taking place, which will eventually reveal them in action.

A poetic and harmonious style of presenting a political perspective, while romanticizing it in order to make it acceptable while pushing the message through, is used in politics and any people movement mobilization to demand public participation in objectives. As a result, it goes beyond the microscopic signals that will one day get embedded in the subconscious of the people, allowing for movement reaction, which is important for political movement to take place.

Music has undoubtedly ignited a social change movement, as has been shown. Campaigns, demonstrations, speeches and debates have all played a role in engaging audiences in politics; there is a new manner of transmitting the political message that is complementary to those who are actively participating in the political conversation. Because of their creative presence and musical participation, musical musicians have propelled political figures ahead, and they have provided a new platform for the distribution of ideas. The grassroots level is where a variety of social problems and concerns connected to political beliefs are being

pushed, since people there are more receptive to these sorts of topics than they are at the upper levels of the government. This area includes topics and concerns relating to race and ethnicity, conflict, poverty, human rights, international order, and social injustice. This is the new revolution, which has been sparked by modern music, and it will continue. In the process, they have ascended to the position of agents of social change. Through the use of lyrics in songs, a message may be delivered to and accepted by a broader audience, regardless of the listener's age, gender, socioeconomic level, or any other demographic characteristics that may be present. Despite the fact that political music is regarded as a distinct genre in and of itself, it is really a mash-up of several genres that have been purposefully blended by great musicians.

However traditional music is typically adapted for political purposes, musical artists who are interested in political music have constructively channeled their musical work and energies to create a special medium in an effort to express their opinions, and they have become increasingly successful in having this type of music resonate with a general audience specifically for the purpose in which it is intended to be performed. The new movements of musical artists who have created songs with political overtones have not only changed the game for politicians who have hired musicians to support their platforms and viewpoints, but they have also changed the conversation about how political and social concerns are handled publicly in general. According to the findings of this research, the introduction of digital media has heralded the beginning of this new age and generated a vast amount of potential for music to achieve what it has already attained. The voice of the times has been heightened as a result of the widespread usage of digital media. It has propelled music, its performers, and the principles they represent, whether they be social or political in nature, to new depths and extremes of expression despite the fact that much remains to be done. On the other hand, social media has had a significant impact on the ability of people to turn the tide of change in their favor. It has had a positive influence on the popularity of music all over the globe. And when it comes to politics, the opportunity to grasp the advantage is alluring. Social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter have enabled political opinions to be widely disseminated, giving them an unique virtual and visual edge over conventional modes of communication.

Individuals' innermost sentiments may be conveyed in a socially acceptable manner via music, which can also be used as a creative instrument. Despite the fact that music has a diverse spectrum of acoustic properties, it has many traits with spoken language. Music and language both rely on rhythm, which may be described as the temporal ordering of apparent events. Rhythm is a fundamental aspect in both. Music's underlying beat, the pulse to which we tap our feet and clap our hands, is known as rhythm. Rhythm is also required for human perception of spoken language in order for it to be understood correctly. When it comes to speech, prosody is a term that refers to the rhythmic and melodic characteristics of the language, which include things like intonation, tone, and emphasis. When it comes to music and speech, rhythm is the vehicle through which meaning is expressed. While the texture and rhythm of a song may be lively and light if it is intended to elicit feelings of joy, it may be slow and desolate if it is intended to elicit feelings of sorrow. Similarly, the texture and rhythm of a song may be sluggish and gloomy if it is intended to elicit feelings of grief or pleasure.

Music interpretation is influenced by the rhythm and melody used, as well as the words we choose to express ourselves in the language that we speak and understand. It has been shown in research that the relevance and appeal of rhythm is a beneficial approach for improving memory performance. As seen by the all-too-common "song stuck in my head" dilemma, music has the ability to become so established in our thoughts that we are unable to dislodge it from our consciousness. Because of this, music is an excellent tool for learning any kind of material or obtaining new knowledge and skills. An enormous amount of literature has been devoted to the advantages of rhythm in memory improvement, and research has shown that include rhythmic components throughout the learning process leads to enhanced information retention regardless of the subject matter under consideration. Apart from improving memory, music has been shown to boost analytical listening ability, cognitive function, confidence, and cultural awareness, to name a few benefits.

In part due to the fact that music is a global language, it has the potential to be a very effective tool for bridging divisions between individuals from various cultures and origins. Music may be considered a medium for international communication since it enables universal notions to be transmitted to individuals from a range of linguistic and cultural backgrounds, regardless of where they come from or what language they speak. The capacity to listen to music is extremely crucial for those who do not yet have the ability to express themselves vocally, due to the universal appeal and positive influence that music has on all people. This attraction, in addition to the other advantages stated in this research review, has been demonstrated to have a statistically significant positive impact on the process of learning a second language, according to the findings of this study review. Music not only assists second language learners in their language acquisition, but it also provides significant insight into the culture of the target language in which they are learning.

When it comes to political music, the potential of the media to have an influence on people's lives has become a watershed moment in the genre's history. In order to increase the likelihood of paying attention to what is being played, a platform where music may be presented in front of an audience that is more inclined to do so as a result of the persuasion of the music and the charisma of the performers must be established. Since

social media sites like as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter are so easily accessible, the huge range of programming available on these platforms has the potential to be a substantial source of interested viewers. In response, music has grown more accessible and powerful, having the capacity to serve as a significant source of knowledge on political themes and to exercise influence over a far larger spectrum of concerns than previously existed.

Because social media is mostly visual, as previously discussed in the article, an attractive photo mixed with suitable lyrics from a song will receive more attention than a visually unappealing image by itself. It is impossible to overstate the importance of using social media for political campaigns and movements. The great amount of power that can be communicated to a larger number of people will be a game changer for both the politicians and their voters. While this is true, artists must exercise care when backing political politicians, since even the most successful campaigns may deteriorate into demonstrations, which can be carried out effectively via the use of social media platforms, as well. In the current context, the capacity of this new generation to transmit messages via music, lyrics, and the usage of social media platforms is very important to their success. As has been evident in recent years, a new link has emerged, and artists have made use of their knowledge, creativity, and musical labor to function as a catalyst for change by connecting their music to political issues and political leaders, in order to effect positive change. Due to their ability to harness their influence and establish themselves as a dominant force in society, they have significantly altered the political climate in which they operate. In part as a result of the use of social media as digital journalism, such artists have elevated their influential power to a new level, allowing them to serve as powerful platforms where political discourse on issues pertaining to politics and society has been amplified and has the ability to resonate with a larger audience and then be cascaded from that point forward. Because of the relationship between musical compositions and politics, not only have they been able to combine the creative power of both the composers and performers to become an extremely effective tool for pushing political themes, but they have also been able to garner significant support for their causes and the politicians who advocate for them. The result of this is that both their influence and the impact of their music bear witness to the reality that music is today regarded as a universal language. According to the book, artists and other creative workers are particularly proficient in this language.

CONCLUSIONS

Propaganda techniques such as politics and social protest songs are used to disseminate a social or political ideology as well as to promote the group cohesiveness of a social or political organization or movement. To begin with, it should be noted that each of these is inextricably related to a certain social or historical environment. Not only does music allow you to express your thoughts and opinions in a peaceful manner by using pleasant sounds rather than aggressive yells and rants, but it is also a highly effective technique of protest because it allows you to express yourself and your values without resorting to physical violence. People from many walks of life who are participating in nonviolent resistance may discover that singing may be a highly useful instrument. While protest songs may have information tentacles that extend both within and beyond the song, this is a positive development. Although it has the capacity to bring about positive change, it also has the potential to get you in legal jeopardy, just as any other form of nonviolent self-expression can.

These songs were composed in the first place as a result of the political circumstances in the nation at the time, which prompted the writing of the songs. They are still in use today, and the passage of time has necessitated the extension of this specific genre as a consequence of the necessity for more material. In an effort to popularize the debate of social concerns in general, a group of artists who are presently involved in political protest music are investigating what may be accomplished by popularizing political protest music. Hosting concerts, distributing music online and offline, and competing with radio stations' top ten song lists are all ways in which they are pushing listeners to take a more in-depth and lengthy look at their surroundings.... The music of social movements, as well as the social movements themselves, are attracting an increasing amount of people's attention these days. Artistic works reveal sensations that are often experienced but seldom addressed via conventional media. There are some topics and concepts that must be spoken and heard, no matter how unpleasant or undesirable they may be for the general public to hear or see. It is a combination of unfettered propaganda, truth-telling, and propaganda, all wrapped together in one package.

An important objective of this research is to examine lesser-known and newer protest sounds, forms (and aesthetics) in their historical contexts, in order to critically recall the origins and meanings of protest songs from the past, particularly those that still have resonance in the present. This research will also look at lesser-known and newer protest sounds, forms (and aesthetics) in their historical contexts. In the articles that follow this one, many iconic songs are investigated using historical approaches and coupled with evolving refrains collected in cutting-edge ethnographies to form a cohesive whole. Philosophical analyses, sociopolitical and economic viewpoints, cultural and contextual interrogations, as well as detailed musicological, textual, and performance studies, all give new and dynamic avenues for protest song research to be studied in greater depth. The researcher has collected and ethnographically investigated and contextualized a wide range of song genres and performance traditions, and he has deliberately broadened the geographical and historical scope of the study

to include places and epochs that are not typical of popular settings in the Philippines. To assist readers comprehend and appreciate the power of music as a social protest vehicle beyond cultural, social, and political barriers, the study should be connected to international music in order to deepen the development and comparison of the findings.

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